

The origin of particles.

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Abstract

This paper shows that you can create all particles from electrons, positrons and neutrinos in a simple and predictable manner. This paper posits the existence of an electro-magnetic structure; the *Maxwell Spin Cup* that gives rise to what appears to be quantised charge. The *Maxwell Spin Cup* consists of two rotating magnetic potentials. The magnetic potentials themselves are displaced forwards and backwards in time from the current time plane. A pair of temporally displaced dipoles is termed a *Sinclair Pair*. The rotating magnetic fields maintain a raised electric potential in the vicinity's of the pair. The paper postulates a time displacement force (a *time like force*) that draws the regions of forward displaced time and backwards displaced time together. The spin of the pair balances the centripetal *time like force*.

A neutrino is then two regions of time displaced space (where the dipoles of the Sinclair Pair align with the spin axis) rotating around each other. The paper sets out the model of the *Maxwell Spin Cup* and proposes a mechanism by which they can be created from high energy photons. There are 4 possible configurations of the simplest *Maxwell Spin Cup* and they correspond to: spin-up-electrons, spin-down-electron, spin-up-positrons, spin-down-positrons.

Cooper pairs are formed via quadrupole attraction between pairs of electrons with opposite spin.

Maxwell Spin Cups can be linked together to form compound particles like *pions*, *protons* and neutrons if time displaced dipoles are shared between two or three Maxwell Spin cups. The overlapping of electrically polarised regions of space account for the apparent charge of quarks ($+/- 1/3, +/- 2/3$). The origin of mass is then the energy stored in the time like bonds between the dipoles in linked Maxwell Spin Cups.

The paper makes a testable prediction that the structure of the neutron is composed of [electron - neutrino - positron] with *time displacement* cross linking between the dipole regions in the associated *Maxwell Spin Cups*.

Keywords: *origin of spin 1/2 particles, origin of quantisation of charge in particles, neutrino spin 1/2 temporal shift*

1 Introduction

Electrons (and positrons) have a series of documented properties:

- quantised charge [7].
- spin of +/- 1/2 [2].
- magnetic dipole moment [9, 8].
- electric dipole moment [11]
- rest mass [4].

Prior to this paper no satisfactory explanation has been given for why particle charge is quantised, what exactly gives rise to a spin 1/2 particle or why an electron should have a magnetic dipole moment or indeed an electric dipole moment. No explanation exists of the process by which a high energy gamma ray photon creates an electron/positron pair at a scattering event or any plausible explanation of what a neutrino is or what it is for.

This paper proposes a stable electro-magnetic structure that we term a *Maxwell Spin Cup* that maintains a region of raised electric potential. It also proposes a mechanism by which such a structure can be created by temporal drag in a scattering event.

The creation process naturally gives rise to a pair of oppositely charged *Maxwell Spin Cups*. Consideration of the creation process and the mysterious nature of spin 1/2 particles leads to the conclusion that it is possible to displace regions of space time *in* time. The displacement in time of a pair of regions, one forwards and one backwards seems to create a force between the regions. A pair of temporally displaced regions rotating about each other will have intrinsic angular momentum, it is likely that if the dipoles regions are aligned N-S, S-N with the spin axis then you have a neutrino (figure ??). We call a pair of temporally displaced rotating regions with dipoles in them a *Sinclair Pair*. It is possible that dark matter is just annoying clouds of neutrinos shed from subatomic processes in stars. These build up over time causing gravity to appear to change over time and short intergalactic distances.

In this model multi-quark particles are created by temporal cross linking of the dipoles in multiple Maxwell Spin Cups. The mass in a compound particle then corresponds to the energy stored in the time like bonds between time entangled spin cups.

This paper is laid out as follows, section 2 illustrates the structure of a *Maxwell Spin Cup* and shows the 4 different configurations that correspond to spin-up-electrons, spin-down-electrons, spin-up-positrons and spin-down-positrons. The differing magnetic quadruple moments of the spin-up and spin-down versions account for the existence of Cooper-pairs. Apparent quantisation of charge results from there being one stable set of values for angular momentum, temporal displacement and spatial displacement in the *Sinclair Pair*. The author speculates that some component of cosmic background radiation results from photon

emission as the electric and magnetic fields in the Maxwell spin cup settle into equilibrium as and electron or positron are formed.

Section 2.2.1 gives the proposed structure of a neutrino showing how a near mass less particle can have spin like properties.

Section 2.1 illustrates how a differential time like drag on a photon can distort it sufficiently to create a pair of *Maxwell Spin Cups*.

Section 3 shows how Maxwell Spin Cups can be compounded into heavy particles through time like cross linking of dipoles in multiple spin cups. The energy in the time like bounds is the origin of mass in compound particles. Sections ?? and ?? proposes a structure for the proton and the neutron. The predicted structure of the neutron naturally has an electric dipole moment.

Future directions are considered and conclusions are given in sections 4 and 5.

2 Maxwell Spin Cups

Figure 2 illustrates a Maxwell Spin Cup. The spin cup comprises two goblets of space time one displaced forwards in time and one displaced backwards in time (a Sinclair Pair), separated by some radial distance, each contains a magnetic potential. The Gobi's of space time rotate around an axis in space. The force that holds the two regions of space together is termed a time like force and is a bit like Heisenberg's uncertainty principle. It is beyond the scope of this paper to justify the existence of the time like force mathematically. This model gives rise to 4 distinct spin cups for the two possible senses of the magnetic fields and two directions of rotation. The magnitudes of the two magnetic potentials are assumed to be equal. It is beyond the scope of this paper to give a mathematical description of the distribution of potential created but it is very likely to have a dipole moment aligned with the spin axis and it is likely to be torroidal in nature.

There are four possible configurations for a simple Maxwell Spin Cup. The magnetic field vectors [5] can be arranged [N-SS-N] or [S-NN-S] and the direction of rotation can be either clockwise or anti-clockwise. The four possible Maxwell Spin Cups are illustrated in figure 2.

The spin up-ness and spin down-ness are governed by the pairings of the magnetic field vectors, either [N-SS-N] or [S-NN-S]. It is obvious that there is the possibility for spin up and spin down electrons to attract each other through rotating quadruple alignment if they share a common spin axis. As one has spin $1/2$ and the other spin $-1/2$ the combined pair will have spin 0. This predicted behaviour corresponds to the creation of Cooper pairs [1]. Neutrinos are made form leptons by changing the directions of the magnetic dipoles. Which dipole is shifted forwards in time accounts for much of the unfathomable behaviour of neutrinos.

Maxwell Spin Cup

Figure 1: A Maxwell Spin Cup with its Sinclair Pair. Rotating magnetic potentials hold the electrical potential in the vicinity of the cup away from zero. The two regions occupied by the magnetic potentials are displaced from each other in time and space. The fuchsia region is forward in time (displaced forward in time from the current time plane) and the blue region is displaced backwards in time.

2.1 Creation of Maxwell Spin Cups

Figure 2.1 shows the electric and magnetic fields of a photon plotted along a time or space axis.

As a photon passes a General Relativistic [3] space-time gradient the wave form is distorted. The distortion will become unstable if the fields become multi-valued for a given portion of the photon.

The energy required in a photon for it to be capable of creating an electron-positron pair is 1.022 MeV in broad terms this corresponds to a wavelength of $1.213 \times 10^{-12}m$. This is going to be an upper bound on order of magnitude of the separation of the two electric field fragments and the temporal separation of the field fragments is going to be of the order of 1/4 of (1/frequency) or about 10^{-20} seconds. The volume in which charge is confined will be smaller than the rotating radius of the *Sinclair Pair*. The quoted classical radius of an electron seems to be $< 2.817910^{-15}m$. The numbers don't appear to be catastrophically

The 8 simple Maxwell Spin Cups

Figure 2: The 8 simple Maxwell Spin Cups for electron-spin-up, electron-spin-down, positron-spin-up, positron-spin-down and a bunch of neutrinos.

different given the length of the arms being waved.

The conditions for a photon shedding a pair of Maxwell Spin Cups is likely to be very specific. The time dilation across the photon will likely have to align portions of the magnetic field that are the same length. The phase of the photon at the alignment point must be such that there is some relation between the energy stored in the magnetic potential and in the electric potential (probably near equality).

2.2 Quantising electric potential into apparent charge

This paper posits a new force created by displacing two regions of space off the current time plain. Heisenberg would have guessed that this force would be a function of the time displacement and the amount of energy involved. In order to create a displacement Newton would have argued you need to push backwards as well as forwards so the force required to create a displacement requires two ends. We call this new kind of force a *time like force*.

The force required to hold two rotating dipoles together (the *time like force* associated with their space and time displacement) must equal the centrifugal force associated with the rotating motion of the regions. It is thought that there are a very small number of stable solutions and this is the source of the quantisation of apparent charge and momentum.

The dipoles in the *Sinclair Pair* in a Maxwell Spin Cup have the property that the wave function appears to be a duplicate of itself after 1/2 a rotation but they are not a direct duplicate until 1 full rotation, this may lead an observer to

Figure 3: Illustrative photon magnetic (blue) and electric (red) field strength along a time/space axis (black).

miss-read the angular momentum. I am just going to wave my arms in the air here and wait for a someone else to do the maths to prove this is the origin of spin 1/2 ness.

The author chooses to speculate that cosmic background radiation is evidence for the width of the stable zone of attraction as a chunk of electric potential and two magnetic dipoles subside into a stable state as an electron or positron is formed in a scattering event. The first spectral peak of cosmic background radiation is at a wavelength of about 2mm [6] or an energy of $6.53 \times 10^{-4} eV$ this compares to the mass of an electron of $0.511 \times 10^6 eV$. So you would guess that the mass of the electron is quantised to probably better than 1 part in 10^{12} which agrees with experiment.

2.2.1 Neutrinos

Given that neutrinos have spin identical to electrons it is probable that you can get a neutrino from an electron by rotating the dipoles to be aligned with the spin axis and for them to point N-S and S-N. This is shown in figure 2.2.1. Neutrinos derived from electrons can have four states:

1. spin 1/2 N-S in Future time, S-N Back in time
2. spin 1/2 N-S Back, S-N Future
3. spin -1/2 N-S B, S-N F
4. spin -1/2 N-S F, S-N B

It seems that it is the presence of a chunk of magnetic field that allows a force to be applied to a region of space time. It seems plausible that it is the continued presence of the field that allows the chunk of space time to remain

Figure 4: Illustrative effect of local time like drag on one side of a photon. Note the blue field line becoming non singular valued as it passes a location with large GR gradient.

distinct, this may not be the case but the author has no way of testing either hypothesis.

So the author will just assert that neutrinos contain a pair of time shifted magnetic dipoles aligned N-S, S-N with the spin axis and wait to be contradicted.

Neutrinos as we will see in the following section can form scattering pits in heavy particles. The sub-atomic scattering process is not entirely charge based as people had assumed.

3 Quarks

Quarks can be created in the fallout form high energy electron-positron collisions. Quarks have innate electrical potential and exist in tightly bound clusters of two or three quarks. The most surprising and interesting property of quarks is that the force between a pair of quarks rises with the distance they are apart (rather than falling of as $\frac{1}{r^2}$ like in some field potential process). The assertion that individual quarks have quantised charge of one of $(+2/3, -2/3, +1/3, -1/3)$ is experimentally derived but is not correct. The origin of the apparent charge results from the overlap of the electrically polarised zones of *Maxwell Spin Cups*

Figure 5: Turning a e^- Maxwell Spin Cup into a neutrino by rotating the dipoles in the Sinclair Pair to align with the spin axis.

in close proximity to each other rather than the existence of some fraction of an abstract quantity called charge.

For brevity we will only present the multiple Maxwell Spin Cup models for the four 3-quark (massive) particles: both kinds of proton, the neutron and a new particle we christen the *lyricon* after the space ship designer in the Hitchhiker's Guide to the Galaxy.

The paper proposes a mechanism for how these particles are created and names the stretched portion of space time they contain (and capped by Maxwell Spin Cups) the *Heisenberg strut*. The paper argues that it is these locked stretchings of space time (the Heisenberg struts) that account for expansion and that the *lyricon* particle is a strong candidate for dark matter. The mechanism by which they are created we call the *Hobson* mechanism and it accounts for how energy is created and held in the universe, it requires specific GR conditions to be met which are referred to as the *Hobson conditions for expansion* and it governs which particles can be created.

3.0.1 protons etc.

Figure 3.0.2 shows the two types of proton, they are: $type1[e^+ - e^- - e^+]$ and $type2[e^+ - \nu - \nu]$ where ν stands for neutrino. A type 1 proton can decay into a neutron by changing the orientation of the dipoles in one of its e^+ spin cups. Similarly a neutron can decay into a *type 2* proton by changing the orientation of the dipoles in its e^- spin cup. A type 2 proton can decay into a *lyricon* particle by flipping its remaining dipoles to be aligned with their spin axis. The Heisenberg struts remain intact giving you a dark particle of about the mass of a proton.

Family of 3- Maxwell Spin Cup particles

Figure 6: Maxwell spin cups for the two kinds of proton, neutron and lyricon particles. The Heisenberg struts are locked in place by the dipoles in the spin cups. The spin cups are held together by time like forces while simultaneously being pushed apart by Heisenberg struts.

3.0.2 Heisenberg Struts

A Heisenberg strut is a stretched portion of space time. It links two Sinclair Pairs where each pair is formed from dipoles from different locations and the bounce back from the relativistic event (meeting the *Hobson conditions*) leads to an internal tension and an external expansion of space time. Figure ?? illustrates the Hobson mechanism for creating Heisenberg struts.

In simple terms Hobson conditions are met when the time difference between spatially distinct dipoles matches the stable radius of a Sinclair Pair. For the formation of a type 1 proton two Heisenberg struts must form. This Hobson process naturally quantises the energy in the Heisenberg strut.

The formation of Heisenberg struts drives the expansion of the universe and creates the energy to go in it. The *lyricon* is the dark matter particle you have been looking for.

The separation of the Maxwell Spin Cups containing the electron and positron has to some degree been estimated and a quoted value is approximately $10^{-15}m$,

Heisenberg strut formation.

dipoles in small gobits of space time.

General Relativistic shear

cross linking to form Sinclair pairs c-2 and d-3

bounce back to form Heisenberg strut.

Expanded space time.

Figure 7: Heisenberg struts are created when dipoles from spatially distinct locations are linked in Sinclair Pairs. Hobson conditions have to be met for them to pair up, rebound from this leads to stretching of space time and an internal force between the Sinclair pairs.

ball park estimation of the electric dipole moment is $1.60210^{-19} \times 10^{-15} = 1.60210^{-34} Cm$. This estimate is based on a point charge approximation, the value for a uniformly distributed charged shell will be a bit higher. This comes in well below the current upper limit determined experimentally of $310^{-26} Cm$ but is definitively non zero.

3.0.3 Heavier cousins

It seems very likely that the heavier versions of the electron, positron and neutrino result from a larger time displacement between the pairs of time displaced dipoles that make up the Sinclair Pair in the Maxwell spin cup. A common geometric form shared across different temporal shifts accounts for the analogous behaviour exhibited in particle families. If you have ever tried spinning a particularly fat American on an office chair you will understand why heavier particles are unstable.

4 Future Work

It remains to crunch the numbers to make sure *Maxwell Spin Cups* can stably exist and have a basin of attraction where if you nearly make one it will bleed off electrical potential and insure magnetic potential rotation matches the time like force that holds them together. The author wondered is there could exist a second type of *Maxwell Spin Cup* in which the *Sinclair Pair* contained an electric potential rather than the familiar magnetic one but the is likely a geometrical reason why this can't result in something stable.

Time displacement from the current time plane is also going to have to be studied and maths for the Heisenberg struts done.

The central remaining question in Physics is: 'Is the time shifted chunk of magnetic dipole at the heart of the Sinclair Pair innately quantised or is the quantisation a result of a stable spin process'.

5 Conclusions

This paper posits a model for a mechanism by which electric potential can be localised and quantised. This shows charge does not exist so there may be nothing intrinsically special about its familiar quantisation. The existence of Cooper-pairs is a function of the the differing sense of the magnetic quadruple like polarisations associated with rotating [N-SS-N] and [S-NN-S] Maxwell Spin Cups. A mechanism is proposed for how scattering events create pairs of *Maxwell Spin Cups*. The paper explains the mechanics of spin 1/2 particles and predicts the existence of neutrinos. Neutrinos are held to contain two magnetic dipoles (shifted in time relative to each other) aligned N-S and S-N along the axis of rotation of the neutrino.

If you assume that the first peak in the cosmic microwave background is associate with the bleeding off of potential to allow a Maxwell Spin Cup to enter the stable state then the charge on the electron is quantised to one part in 10^{-12} .

This paper invents Heisenberg struts. This paper asserts that multi-quark particles arise when dipoles in multiple Maxwell Spin Cups are linked by Heisenberg struts.

The paper predicts that the neutron is comprised of a [electron - positron - neutrino] like set of Maxwell Spin Cups linked by Heisenberg struts and makes a ballpark prediction of its dipole moment and it is small but non zero and does not disagree with experimental determined values. It predicts there are two types of proton and a new dark matter particle called a *lyricon* which is three neutrinos held apart by Heisenberg struts.

The paper offers a mechanism (the Hobson mechanism) that accounts for how energy is created as space time is expanded (and held open by Heisenberg struts).

In reality (physics) no additional dimensions are required only Maxwell's equations and General Relativity. The new idea is that you can create a force in space by displacing two regions of space time away form the current time plane.

All of the quandaries about point charges are irrelevant, any theory that relies on the intrinsic quantisation of charge is no longer justifiable (because charge does not exist). It short, wave functions are fine, but charge as an abstract quantity does not exist.

6 Acknowledgements

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References

- [1] J. Bardeen, L. N. Cooper, and J. R. Schrieffer. Theory of superconductivity. *Phys. Rev.*, 108:1175–1204, Dec 1957. doi: 10.1103/PhysRev.108.1175. URL <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRev.108.1175>.
- [2] Jeremy Bernstein. The stern gerlach experiment, 2010. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/1007.2435>.
- [3] A. Einstein. The foundation of the general theory of relativity. 1916.
- [4] Dean L Farnham, Robert S Van Dyck Jr, and Paul B Schwinberg. Determination of the electron's atomic mass and the proton/electron mass ratio via penning trap mass spectroscopy. *Physical review letters*, 75(20):3598, 1995.
- [5] David J Griffiths. *Introduction to electrodynamics*. Pearson, 2013.
- [6] John C Mather, ES Cheng, David A Cottingham, RE Eplee Jr, Dale J Fixsen, Tilak Hewagama, RB Isaacman, KA Jensen, Stephan S Meyer, Peter D Noerdlinger, et al. Measurement of the cosmic microwave background spectrum by the coBE FIRAS instrument. *The Astrophysical Journal, Part 1 (ISSN 0004-637X)*, vol. 420, no. 2, p. 439-444, 420:439-444, 1994.
- [7] Robert Andrews Millikan. On the elementary electrical charge and the avogadro constant. *Physical Review*, 2(2):109, 1913.
- [8] C. Quigg. Notes on lepton gyromagnetic ratios. 2023. URL <https://lss.fnal.gov/archive/test-fn/1000/fermilab-fn-1129-t.pdf>.
- [9] John Tit. Electron magnetic dipole moment. 2023. URL https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Electron_magnetic_moment.
- [10] John Tit. Knot physics. 2027. URL <https://www.knotphysics.net>.

- [11] W. C. Yi and T. J. Carroll. Electron electric dipole moment searches using clock transitions in ultracold molecules. *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 125:153201, 2020. doi: 10.1103/PhysRevLett.125.153201.